

ESG reporting meets farmer – implications of the European corporate sustainability reporting directive for the agrifood sector

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Abstract

Purpose – Focusing on food companies and farmers, this paper investigates implications of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) for the Danish agrifood sector.

Design/methodology/approach – We used an explorative approach, conducting semi-structured interviews with sustainability experts from the Danish agrifood sector and applying institutional theory to analyze the data, focusing on institutional pressures and anticipated behavioral responses.

Findings – Our findings show multiple implications of the CSRD for the Danish agrifood sector through an interplay of institutional pressures that act beyond their coercive nature. Pressures are not only exerted on targeted companies but also indirectly on farmers in the value chain due to an increased data demand. The results suggest acquiescence as a most likely behavioral response, and we highlight the need for sector-wide harmonization of farm-level data to increase the potential of the directive to contribute to sustainable development of the Danish agrifood sector.

Originality/value – This study is the first to analyze and discuss the wider sectoral implications of the CSRD for the agrifood sector. Through this, we deepen the understanding of institutional pressures of mandatory sustainability reporting directives and add to the small body of literature that analyses implications of sustainability reporting in the agrifood sector beyond its financial effects.

Keywords Mandatory non-financial disclosure, ESG, CSRD, Sustainability reporting and impact, Food value chain, Agrifood, Sustainable development

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

The agrifood sector holds a unique role in the global transition to sustainable development (WSSD, 2002), as it has significant environmental and social impacts along its supply chains (Chen *et al.*, 2018; Foley *et al.*, 2011; Kunz *et al.*, 2023). The agrifood sector is the main contributor to the transgression of several planetary boundaries (Campbell *et al.*, 2017), while also being heavily dependent on limited natural resources and vulnerable to external influences such as climate change (Tao *et al.*, 2011). To demonstrate how corporates address these various challenges in their own operations and along their supply chains, the disclosure of environmental, social and governance (ESG) information has become an increasingly common practice by corporates, also in the agrifood sector (Conca *et al.*, 2021). Corporates face increasing demand for ESG information from stakeholders and shareholders (Abate *et al.*, 2021; Arvidsson and Dumay, 2022). In the EU, for non-listed companies, this reporting has mostly been voluntary and heterogeneous (Aboud *et al.*, 2023), although the Non-Financial

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Reporting Directive (NFRD) (2014/95/EU) has imposed some requirements on large listed companies since 2018.

To further streamline reporting requirements, the EU introduced the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). From 2024 onwards, the CSRD mandates ESG disclosures from a larger number of companies and provides a more detailed reporting framework compared to the NFRD. With its expanded scope and stricter requirements, the CSRD is likely to have a greater impact on the agrifood sector compared to previous frameworks (a detailed comparison of the CSRD and the NFRD is found in [Section 2](#)).

The current literature on ESG reporting is mostly found in the field of accounting, management and finance ([Senadheera et al., 2022](#)). Through a bibliometric and content analysis, [Jain and Tripathi \(2023\)](#) identify *ESG investments* and *ESG and firm value* as the most frequently addressed topics in ESG literature. In a scoping review of sustainability reporting studies in Europe, [Dinh et al. \(2023\)](#) observed a similar tendency, with most reviewed studies focusing on the economic effects of ESG reporting, such as financial performance and market reaction. Similar trends were evident in ESG literature that specifically examined the agrifood sector: In a literature review, [Leite De Almeida et al. \(2024\)](#) found research on ESG in the agricultural sector to still be limited and in its early phases, with a majority of the research focusing on either “Sustainable finance and investments” or “Data disclosure and corporate performance”. Several recent studies analyze the financial effects between ESG disclosure or ESG ratings and the financial effects for agrifood companies ([Brunella et al., 2024](#); [Buallay, 2022a, b](#); [Conca et al., 2021](#); [Coppola et al., 2020](#); [Cupertino et al., 2021](#); [Nirino et al., 2019](#); [Pirtea et al., 2021](#); [Sandberg et al., 2022](#); [Vitale et al., 2023](#)). Studies that extend their analysis to include factors beyond financial effects typically focus more in-depth on the content and quality of food companies’ sustainability reports. For example, [Bellantuono et al. \(2018\)](#) looked at how to optimize the material analysis for ESG reports of agrifood companies and [Orou Sannou et al. \(2023\)](#) suggested how to better implement social perspectives into the sustainability assessment of agrifood companies. Moreover, [Anguiano-Santos and Salazar-Ordóñez \(2024\)](#) analyze the overall quality of ESG reports of Spanish agrifood companies, whereas [Boiral et al. \(2024\)](#) focus specifically on the risk disclosure in ESG reports of agrifood companies.

There is a notable bias in the literature for the agrifood sector, with a strong focus on financial effects or very narrow aspects of ESG reporting. Further, many studies are single case studies, often limited to one or a few companies. We therefore argue that there is a gap in research adopting a broader, sectoral lens, which is essential to better understand how ESG reporting affects the agrifood sector, including the relationship between farmers and companies. This is important because the quality of food companies’ reports ultimately depends on the quality and quantity of data received from farmers in their value chain. This is especially relevant when the data should be used to mitigate negative impacts, as farms represent the area where agrifood companies have the highest environmental impact in their value chains ([Harwatt et al., 2024](#); [Poore and Nemecek, 2018](#)). Further, none of the aforementioned studies focus on the CSRD as a regulatory framework. As we will outline in [Section 2](#), the CSRD is the most ambitious ESG reporting framework to date ([Baks, 2024](#)) and therefore the implications for agrifood companies will likely also differ substantially compared to previous frameworks, highlighting the need to critically address this new directive.

To address this research gap, we conducted an explorative study. Through expert interviews and applying the lens of institutional theory, we first aim to explore the implications of the CSRD on the food sector and the anticipated behavioral responses from farmers and food companies. This is of high relevance because the pressures experienced and the behavioral responses of both farmers and companies can influence the quality of the ESG reports. Only if ESG reports and their underlying data are of high quality can market discipline function and potentially contribute to the sustainable development of the agrifood sector. Secondly, we aim to place the implications exerted by the CSRD into the broader context of existing sustainability initiatives and pressures to better understand to what extent they could potentially contribute to the sector’s sustainable development.

We focus on Denmark to exemplify these general challenges. Similar to other EU cases, the Danish agrifood sector is heavily influenced by institutional pressures exerted through regulations and directives (Debonne *et al.*, 2022). Agricultural primary production is especially shaped by the Common Agricultural Policy and European regulations such as the EU Nature Law, EU Nitrate Directive, the Water Framework Directive or sectoral greenhouse gas emissions reduction targets, among others. What distinguishes the Danish agrifood case is its intensity, high specialization and export orientation (Klimek and Hansen, 2017). Further it has a close relationship between farmers and companies, since several of Denmark's largest food companies are farmers' cooperatives (Averbuch *et al.*, 2021) (e.g. Arla Foods and Danish Crown). Moreover, in comparison to other EU countries, the farm-level data availability and digitalization of the sector is very high in Denmark (Șerbănel, 2021). Therefore, we argue that Denmark is a critical case in the sense that it can provide insights on the implications of the CSRD under comparatively optimal conditions in the agricultural sector, from which other EU countries can learn.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a short overview of the CSRD and its novelty compared to previous sustainability regulation in Europe. Section 3 outlines our methodology, followed by a theoretical introduction in Section 4. The results are displayed in Section 5 and discussed in Section 6. Finally, conclusions and perspectives are presented.

2. Overview of the CSRD and ESRS

The CSRD aims to standardize ESG reporting across the EU and to significantly increase its quality (European Commission, 2023). It revises the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) (2014/95/EU), expanding its scope to approximately 50,000 European companies, compared to the NFRD's 11,700. The CSRD affects both large listed companies (beginning in 2024) and large non-listed companies fulfilling two of the following three criteria: (1) more than 250 employees, (2) more than €40 million in net turnover, (3) more than €20 million in assets (starting in 2025). Listed small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) will be required to report under the CSRD after 2026 (European Commission, 2023). Several large Danish food cooperatives, including the dairy cooperative Arla and the meat cooperative Danish Crown, were not previously required to report under the NFRD, but will now be mandated to report under the CSRD.

The introduction of the NFRD in 2018 is seen as a first and important step toward mandatory sustainability reporting in the EU (Ottenstein *et al.*, 2022), increasing the reporting of ESG information in Europe (Conte, 2024). However, after being in place for several years and with growing interest in corporate sustainability information and increasing concerns about greenwashing, the NFRD was considered insufficient to guide a transparent disclosure of (un-) sustainable corporate behavior (Beck, 2024; Chicchini *et al.*, 2024). Krasodomska *et al.* (2024) highlight "insufficiently detailed requirements, myriad of overlapping and sometimes inconsistent reporting frameworks and standards, and lack of enforcement and credibility of the disclosures provided" as the reasons for the NFRD's to keep up with growing expectations for sustainability reporting.

To tackle these shortcomings, the CSRD introduced several new mechanisms that essentially differentiate it from its predecessor. First and foremost, instead of giving companies flexibility in choosing which standard they want to report under (such as the GRI), the CSRD mandates the use of the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) (European Commission, 2023), providing a common, harmonized reporting standard. The ESRS impose detailed reporting requirements including more granular data than the standards used under the NFRD. The ESRS specify the content, including impacts, risks and opportunities, and data points companies must report on, regarding two cross-cutting standards and 10 topical standards (European Commission, 2023) (Table 1). Each of these topical standards is specified further by several disclosure requirements and data points.

Table 1. Topical standards of the ESRS

Cross-cutting	ESRS 1: General principles ESRS 2: General disclosures
Environment	ESRS E1: Climate Change ESRS E2: Pollution ESRS E3: Water and marine sources ESRS E4: Biodiversity and ecosystems ESRS E5: Resource and circular economy
Social	ESRS S1: Own workforce ESRS S2: Workers in the value chain ESRS S3: Affected communities ESRS S4: Consumers and end users
Governance	ESRS G1: Business conduct
Source(s): Authors' own work	

Secondly, together with the ESRS, the CSRD introduced the concept of double materiality to determine which topics companies should report on. A company is required to report on topics that meet the criteria for either impact materiality or financial materiality—or both. Impact materiality describes the actual or potential impacts of a company and its value chain on either people or the environment. Financial materiality describes the financial effects (risks or opportunities) that the respective topic has on a company (European Commission, 2023). The introduction of the double-materiality principle can be seen as paradigm shift in assessing what information is important to disclose. Previous reporting standards have shown a strong tendency to focus only on financial materiality (Wassénius *et al.*, 2024), thus neglecting the coverage of material environmental or social impacts. The dual perspective of the CSRD thus promises to expand the scope of reported information significantly, furthermore, so through explicitly including value chain impacts. This is of specific relevance for the agrifood sector, whose supply chains have significant environmental impacts (Willett *et al.*, 2019).

Thirdly, the CSRD introduced the requirement of first limited and later reasonable mandatory assurance for the sustainability statements, a level of scrutiny not required under the NFRD. Mandatory assurance is said to increase the credibility of the information disclosed in the sustainability statements (Krasodomska *et al.*, 2024) and as a necessity to get sustainability reporting on par with financial reporting (Krasodomska *et al.*, 2021)

These significant advancements of the CSRD compared to previous reporting frameworks mark a “milestone shift” in sustainable reporting (Beck, 2024). We thus anticipate the directive to have significant organizational and structural implications for the Danish agrifood sector that make it imperative to analyze how these will play out.

3. Theoretical framework: institutional pressures and strategic responses in ESG reporting

We use institutional theory to analyze how the CSRD will affect the Danish food sector. Institutional theory provides a robust perspective for understanding how external influences, such as regulations, shape and impact organizational behavior (Pinheiro *et al.*, 2023), arguing that companies' strategies are shaped by external pressures in their pursuit of legitimacy (Hirsch, 1975).

As a rationale to explain how organizational behavior is influenced by laws, rules, cultures and norms (Weber, 2014), institutional theory focuses on three so-called institutional pressures, first described by DiMaggio and Powell's (1983): (1) Coercive pressures are pressures that an organization receives from powerful stakeholders, typically governments, political institutions or powerful business partners, through, e.g. the enforcement of new regulations (Herold, 2018). As such, the CSRD will line up with previous regulation in the EU,

where coercive pressures of regulation traditionally shaped sustainability reporting stronger than in other international contexts (Higgins and Larringa, 2014). (2) The second institutional pressure is enacted through mimetic mechanisms (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Mimetic behavior occurs when companies imitate the behaviors of their successful competitors to achieve the same success and therefore increase their own legitimacy (Latif *et al.*, 2020). Although hard to prove empirically, Higgins and Larringa (2014) argue that this is relevant in ESG reporting and is a reason why multinational companies publish reports even when they were not mandated to do so. (3) Lastly, normative pressures describe pressures which companies experience from suppliers, customers, NGOs, the media and other social entities. These pressures usually force companies to prove their behavior is not injustice (Latif *et al.*, 2020). In the case of ESG reporting, companies may also do it, simply put, because it is “the right thing to do” (Higgins and Larringa, 2014). It should be noted that the pressures of these three mechanisms are not operationally and analytically distinct but often interlinked (Hoffman, 1999). As an example, the institutionalization of ESG reporting under the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) happened through a mix of all three mechanisms after having originally started out from normative pressures (Livesey, 2001).

Due to different institutional pressures, institutional theory argues that a process called isomorphism will take place over time: If different companies receive the same institutional pressures, they will adopt similar strategies and logics to gain legitimacy. This means that not only do companies start sustainability reporting in the first place as a result of external pressures, but that the sustainability reporting between the different companies will eventually become more similar (Herold, 2018).

We find institutional theory to be particularly relevant for examining the implications of the CSRD for Danish agrifood companies. Institutional theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how external influences, exerted through the CSRD, shape organizational practices, including ESG reporting processes (Herold, 2018). It offers a broader perspective on ESG reporting than, e.g. legitimacy theory (Higgins and Larringa, 2014) and is suited for analyzing sector-wide transformations rather than focusing on individual organizations. This broader scope aligns with our objective of exploring the implications of the CSRD at a sectoral level.

There are several transformative requirements of the CSRD, including the double materiality principle, an expanded reporting scope, mandatory third-party verification and a reporting standard through the ESRS, which will likely introduce new or enhance already existing institutional pressures within the Danish food sector. For instance, enhanced scrutiny through mandatory assurance suggests stronger coercive mechanisms than in previous frameworks such as the NFRD. Also, the general expanded scope to approximately 50,000 EU companies, combined with the inclusion of value chain information for the double materiality assessment, could introduce higher normative pressures within the sector. Furthermore, by embedding these requirements into law, the CSRD introduces uniformity, reducing the heterogeneity observed in voluntary frameworks such as the GRI, therefore suggesting increased isomorphism.

However, institutional theory has been criticized for focusing too much on isomorphism and its lack of ability to explain divergence in corporate behavior to ESG-related topics (Herold, 2018; Lee, 2011). Thus, to better understand the responses to the CSRD and move beyond the institutional pressures, we draw on Oliver’s (1991) five strategic responses of organizations to these pressures: Acquiescence (obeying of rules and frameworks and accepting new frameworks and their implications), Compromising (balancing and negotiating the expectations of different stakeholders), Avoidance (escaping the institutional pressure through changing goals, activates or domains), Defiance (ignoring and contesting rules and requirements or assaulting their sources) and Manipulation (dominating institutional constituents and shaping values and criteria) (Oliver, 1991). Which of these behavioral responses an organization will adopt can be approximated by five different institutional factors: Cause (why is the pressure exerted?), Constituent (who is exerting the pressure?),

Content (what are the requirements and norms the organization is being pressured to conform to?), Control (how is the pressure exerted?) and Context (where does the pressure occur?) (Oliver, 1991). Using Oliver's (1991) framework can help including the role of agency of the actors in the agrifood chain and explain potential diverging behavior between them (Lee, 2011).

4. Methods

We employed an abductive approach to investigate the anticipated implications of the CSRD for the Danish sector. This approach is particularly suited for the explorative nature of our study, where the data collection and analysis are iterative. Instead of testing a predefined hypothesis, the study aims to generate insights through an open-ended, iterative process for explorative data collection and using institutional theory to subsequently structure and categorize the collected data.

The data was collected through semi-structured interviews (Adams, 2015) with 13 stakeholders as key informants along the Danish agrifood value chain (Table 2), including positions in food companies, agricultural advisory services, consulting companies and interest organizations. Interviewees were initially identified based on desktop research on prominent Danish food cooperatives and advisory firms, and subsequently contacts were gathered using a snowball sampling approach.

The informants were chosen based on their expertise in sustainability reporting and involvement in the reporting under the CSRD. All interviewees were required to have expertise in sustainability reporting, regardless of their organizational affiliation.

The iterative process of data collection and theory refinement was operationalized as follows: The interviews followed an initial interview guide which was loosely informed by institutional theory and DiMaggio and Powell's (1983) institutional pressures but in its structure more guided by explorative practical considerations. It began with general questions about ESG reporting in the agricultural sector, focusing on the motivation behind it, demand development and voluntary standards used. Afterward, the guide covered questions about the CSRD's impacts and implications for stakeholders along the food value chain, focusing on companies and farmers. This included questions about internal processes, preparation for the CSRD, data management, financial impacts, and general chances and challenges of the new framework. Consistent with the nature of semi-structured interviews, these questions were a mix of open- and close-ended questions which were adapted for each stakeholder and iteratively during the conversation, instead of following a set of narrow questions in a strict

Table 2. Overview of the informants

ID	Sector	Position
1	Food Company	Head of ESG Reporting
2	Food Company	Head of ESG Reporting
3	Food Company	Head of Sustainable Agricultural Development
4	Food Company	Head of ESG Reporting
5	Food Company	Business Controller/Agricultural Consultant
6	Food Company	Head of global marketing and sustainability
7	Agricultural Consultant Company	Economic and sustainability advisor
8	General Consultant Company	Sustainability advisor
9	Agricultural Consultant Company	Climate- and sustainability advisor
10	Research and Development	Head of Environment and Climate
11	Research and Development	Sustainable Development Advisor
12	Interest Organization	CEO
13	Interest Organization	Head sustainability advisor

Source(s): Authors' own work

thematic order. During the interview series and the initial processing of data, the interview guide and theoretical concepts were refined, e.g. by further expanding it beyond institutional pressures and including Oliver's (1991) behavioral responses allowing for a deeper understanding of the CSRD's implications for the agrifood sector. This reflective process continued throughout the study, ensuring that the final analysis reflected both empirical insights and theoretical evolution. Finally, data was thematically coded into three overall categories of institutional theory – institutional pressures, isomorphism and behavioral responses – and categorized for different stakeholder types, respectively. Quotes were selected and translated as illustrations of stakeholders' reflections and to highlight recurring themes.

Interviews took place between February 28th and April 27th, 2023, during which the ESRS were in its second draft form, published in October 2022. Conceptual changes exist between this draft and the version later taken up by the EU Commission, but the content of the topical standards and sustainability metrics largely overlap.

5. Results

5.1 Coercive pressures

According to several informants, actors along the food value chain experience different coercive pressures due to the CSRD. The CSRD is first seen in its legislative nature as an EU directive with an inherent coercive nature. This became clear in the qualitative analysis, in which the rationale behind the CSRD reporting remained unquestioned. Consequently, the coercive pressure intrinsic to the CSRD is inherently given *a priori*, encapsulated within its legal status. In the interviews, this was expressed by several participants, who stated that in the first years of the CSRD, the focus will be on simply complying with the framework, or as expressed by one company: *“For now, it is not about whether we like it or not. It is simply a requirement”*.

Even though most farms are not directly affected by the CSRD, interview participants pointed out that farmers nevertheless experience coercive pressures in the form of increased data demand, exerted on them by two different kinds of stakeholders. Firstly, the food companies to which the farmers are delivering are asking for farm-level ESG information to disclose their sub-topical standards. Secondly, several interview participants stated investors and financial institutions as stakeholders which increasingly demand ESG information from farms. This is illustrated in this quote from an interview with an agricultural consultant company:

They're asking upon it, the stakeholders. The farmer is still a bit more waiting for what he is actually going to deliver on. But the guys with the money, they want to know everything they [the farmers] are doing. So that's probably where the request comes from.

As farmers depend on financial resources from companies in the form of payment for their products, their data request is perceived as a coercive pressure. Especially the Danish agricultural market is characterized by few, large food producers, leaving farmers limited alternative choices when they experience increased pressure from the company they are currently delivering to. This coercive force is exemplified in the following quote by an agricultural advisor:

I think this is where at least the big companies have some muscles, right? Because they can say, if you don't provide this, well, we will just not use you as a supplier anymore. This could be a really big challenge for the farmers.

Due to this coercive pressure, several informants expect a high bureaucratic burden for farmers, in the form of an increased workload to report the necessary data to stakeholders who are asking for it. When asked if the reporting will be too much work and bureaucracy for the farmers, an advisor responded:

The short answer would be yes, because they already have a lot of things to do. But I don't think it's something they can avoid. That's why the role of the advisory sector is so important to make it as simple as possible.

Other informants expect this burden to be too high if farmers must report their sustainability information to several different stakeholders, using different forms and data sheets. This could initially be hard to avoid:

[The companies are] interested in climate, animal welfare, resource usage, pesticides, things like that. Because it's something that ends up in the final products. For the bank, it's completely different. They are, for instance, much more interested in governance, social security, risk management. So obviously, the reporting formats and the content of the reports will differ.

5.2 Normative pressures

Normative pressures on food companies were reflected in the widespread agreement among all interview participants that the demand for ESG information has generally increased in the run-up to the CSRD. It was stated that this demand comes from different stakeholders, such as customers, investors, financial institutions but also consumers and the public in general. One participant stated that the ESG demand in the agrifood sector has been currently “*exploding*”. “*Especially customers, large customers, [...] are very interested. [...]. Specifically in emission data.*”

Thus, to satisfy stakeholder needs and creating a business value, companies were voluntarily reporting non-financial information beyond the legal requirements in Denmark. Illustrated in the below quote from a large food company:

We've been reporting on our CO₂ emissions, on animal welfare, on a lot of different stuff, because we think it's important for our stakeholders. It's not something that we had to do, but something that we feel brings value.

Another driver mentioned for voluntarily ESG disclosure is that of keeping legitimacy due to normative pressures from society. Especially since climate and animal-welfare related issues are highest on the public agenda, one company stated the importance to be transparent about one's impacts on these issues: “*[The topic] which has the highest political focus within our area and in our industry, is anything related to climate, and anything related to animal welfare.*”

5.3 Mimetic behavior

Mimetic behavior under the ESG reporting under the CSRD is indicated by several reasons. Interviewees highlight that the CSRD allows for a comparison between different companies, giving companies that perform well the opportunity to use their sustainability reports as a competitive advantage in communication strategies, which implies the assumption that sustainability reports will converge in form and content as a requirement to achieve comparability.

The interviews suggest that the market dominance of few food companies in Denmark will likely set the pace for smaller companies, driving mimetic behavior for these. For example, one company stated that they will orientate their ESG disclosure to another firm which described themselves as sustainability frontrunners. The CSRD's implementation timeline might support this behavior. The first companies to start reporting in 2025 are those that previously reported under the NFRD and thus already have experience in filing non-financial information under an official EU framework. These will be followed by the companies which fulfill the CSRD scope and later by the small and medium companies.

The interviews revealed an uncertainty amongst the interviewees regarding the disclosure requirements: “*What's the methodology behind it? How do you do it? What's okay? What's too much? What's too little? I don't know yet*”. It was furthermore stated that everyone working

with the CSRD knows that disclosure is difficult and that “*it’s a process and you can’t be good a everything in the beginning.*” This agrees with other statements saying that the reporting will be a work in progress and adjustments in the reporting are likely even after publishing the first official reports. These general uncertainties mentioned can also serve as an incentive for imitative behavior among companies.

In the interviews, several participants compared the reporting under the CSRD with their financial reporting, suggesting that internal structures and processes from the financial reporting are likely to be imitated under the CSRD to achieve a similar quality of non-financial reports. This can be interpreted as a form of internal mimetic behavior.

5.4 Isomorphism

In the previous ESG reporting of the companies, isomorphism was partly observable. The reporting between companies differed in structure and quantity but also overlaps for reporting frameworks were observable. The Science Based Targets Initiative (SBTi) and Global Reporting Initiative were the most used frameworks among interviewed companies.

The interviews present multiple reasons to expect isomorphism in the reporting under the CSRD. There was a firm agreement between the participants that getting a standardized framework in the form of the ESRS is needed and that they generally welcome receiving such a framework, as it creates a more equal playing field and fairer competition and reduces the risks of greenwashing, especially because of its mandatory external assurance. As the purpose of the CSRD is to standardize ESG reporting and the interview partners were in favor of this standardization, an isomorphic reaction to the new reporting framework can be expected.

Isomorphism can further be driven by consulting companies, potentially guiding companies with standardized procedures for compliance. Because of the companies’ anticipated high workload and uncertainty in regard to the framework, many informants expected that companies will rely on external advisors for CSRD reporting. Even when the aim is to do all the reporting themselves, which according to several informants need at least one full-time employee, consulting firms will be needed initially.

I do think that we either need Danish Industry or PWC or someone else to kind of guide us a bit the next two years in when to do what. So, we make sure that we deliver what we need to deliver but also spend our time wisely and on the right things.

Several arguments were, however, mentioned in the interviews which argue against complete isomorphism under the CSRD. Firstly, the double materiality assessment allows for flexibility in the reporting, depending on which topical standards are defined material by the company. Albeit operating in the same sector, interview participants stated that it is unlikely that the material information is completely uniform between the different food companies.

The reported information and its level of detail further depends on the data availability of the companies, specifically on value chain information. The difficulty of getting the data depends on the topical standard for which material data needs to be disclosed. Since many of the companies already reported under the SBTi, disclosing climate data was not explicitly considered difficult by most interview partners. The judgments of the participants on the difficulty of the other sub-topics differed. One subtopic which most informants considered to be difficult to report is E4 – biodiversity. Two companies which already intensively collected farm-level ESG data were confident of having the right data at hand for the reporting. On the contrary, other companies stated that receiving upstream value chain data in time for the CSRD will partly not be possible and they will work with estimates in the beginning. Accordingly, especially in the early stages of the reporting, complete isomorphism seems unlikely.

5.5 Institutional responses

The interview results suggest acquiescence to be the most likely response of food companies to the CSRD. The framework itself was welcomed by most informants, and at the time of the

interviews every company except one had already started preparations for the disclosure, indicating that they do not want to be hit by the CSRD by surprise once it is fully in place. This is also indicated by the large number of consulting requests the consulting companies are already experiencing:

We see many, many clients coming. And that's also because the standards are so comprehensive and because there are some really big things, for example, like a double materiality assessment, you need to do, where guidance is still lacking.

Several companies stated that they plan to use the reporting to derive strategic value from the reported data and information, reflecting a response of acquiescence. The assumption of acquiescence is further strengthened as there were no direct answers from the interviews which showed planned responses of manipulation, defiance or avoidance to the CSRD.

However, the results also partly indicate a compromise as an anticipated response to the CSRD requirements. This does not mean the attempt of complete avoidance of the reporting, but, for example, reducing the reporting on several sub-topics by defining them as not material. Because the reporting is so resource intensive, especially for smaller firms, different participants have raised concerns that some companies will try to find workarounds for the disclosure. According to different informants, a way in which this potentially could be done is through defining some topics are not material, even though they in fact are. One company highlighted:

It is my expectation that everywhere where it's possible to not report, the firms will not report. [...] they will twist and turn. [...]. For example, there are so many social topics that we can avoid reporting on if we define them as immaterial operations.

The results also indicate that the reason for a compromise as a response, instead of acquiescence, is not necessarily a lack of willingness but rather a lack of ability and resources to comply with the CSRD fully. Especially the difficulties for SMEs in complying with the CSRD have been highlighted by many interview participants, as they lack the necessary resources and the CSRD is too complex to have an untrained employee doing it. This was stressed by one informant:

I think it will be a huge task for especially smaller companies. I believe the really large ones will be fine [...]. But some of the smaller meatpackers, for instance, slaughterhouses, they'll also be affected by this. And I don't think that they've got employees today that are able to do this task. There's going to be a huge demand for people who are able to do this. So, I guess the advisory firms, they're really just going to make a whole lot of money here. [...] It's a development that we can't stop, but I'm nervous that a system will be created that will be really difficult for especially the smaller food companies to deliver on.

Consequently, several participants anticipated that the reporting under the CSRD will partly just be a legal compliance exercise for some, relying on consultants to comply.

Informants further highlighted a discrepancy between the accounting-focused perspective on ESG commonly held by consultants and a more natural-scientific comprehension of sustainability topics within the agri-food sector, as typically embraced by sector employees. A sustainability manager from a food company further elaborates:

I fear a bit that some don't deal with the fact that there are certain [natural] processes that cannot be controlled. I'm really worried that the theory and many people who work with it simply won't be able to understand the agricultural technical knowledge. [...] Depending on whether you come from the financial sector or are a natural scientist, it's sometimes difficult to come to an agreement.

Regarding the behavioral response of farmers, several participants stated that they generally observe an increased sustainability awareness of Danish farmers. However, interview participants stated they believe that there are very few farmers who would report ESG information out of ideological reasons, that there is low intrinsic motivation from farmers to disclose ESG information and instead an antipathy of reporting their data. One participant

stated that their companies' value chain farmers have an opposition to "*putting everything into numbers*". Therefore, agricultural advisors anticipated the farmers to be overwhelmed by the amount of reporting. Nevertheless, acquiescence is expected as the farmer's main response, as various informants expect the sustainability data disclosure of farmers to be a license to operate in the future.

Several interview participants believe that the coercive force exerted on the farmers through the CSRD might be a push for the structural farm development in Denmark, meaning that an increasing number of small farms will need stop production. This was exemplified by one informant through a personal example:

I'm sure that it'll be a large burden especially for the smaller farmers. My own father had a farm with 40 cows, and luckily, he sold it now, but I can't imagine him delivering on all these new requirements. But if you have a huge production with several hundred animals and several employees, then it might be easier for you. But it's something that will push the structural development again, I guess, on farming. So, there'll be less and less room for the small farmers who can't deliver on all these requirements.

6. Discussion

In the upcoming section, our findings will be contextualized within broader discussions in the agricultural sector, with a specific emphasis on integration with existing initiatives and its impact on sustainability.

In this study we first aimed to explore the institutional pressures exerted by the CSRD on the agrifood sector. Our results foremost revealed that the CSRD is anticipated to have manifold sectoral implications. Mainly present through its coercive nature which targets large food companies, the CSRD catalyzed an interplay of normative, and mimetic pressures on different actors along the value chain. As a response to these pressures, acquiescence and potentially compromising are anticipated as the most common responses. These findings are in line with previous studies that found that the NFRD (Aureli *et al.*, 2020) and GRI (Livesey, 2001) exerted institutional pressures beyond their initial coercive and normative pressures, respectively, and instead showed an interplay of institutional pressures and responses.

This interplay of pressures has the potential to create tensions and complexities in corporate behavior, as evidenced in our findings. The coercive pressures stemming from the legal mandate of the CSRD were highlighted as a key driver for companies to prioritize compliance, often in a resource-intensive manner. Thus, the coercive pressure of the directive itself might only lead corporates to focus on meeting minimum requirements. However, the coercive pressures from other stakeholders (e.g. powerful companies and financial institutions), as well as normative pressures, were seen as a leverage for pushing companies beyond mere compliance.

These different strengths of pressures experienced further depend on where in the value chain the actor is located. Interestingly, the results partly suggest that even though the CSRD targets large companies (and at a later stage listed SMEs), farmers at the lower end of the value chain to potentially experience the strongest institutional pressures. This was highlighted by several informants, taking the limited resources of farmers into consideration.

This interplay and potential conflicts of institutional pressures is reflected in the behavioral responses of the actors in the agrifood sector. The anticipated responses of acquiescence and compromise (Oliver, 1991) to the experienced institutional pressures are not necessarily dichotomous; instead, the results suggest these responses can be flexible and contingent on individual circumstances. For instance, while acquiescence appears to be the dominant response among both companies and farmers, who view compliance with the CSRD as inevitable, compromise is evident in efforts to navigate resource constraints or align reporting practices with existing initiatives. This flexibility allows actors to adapt their strategies based on factors such as organizational capacity, stakeholder demands and sector-specific dynamics.

The interplay of these responses underscores the nuanced ways in which companies and farmers are managing the pressures exerted by the CSRD, reflecting a spectrum of strategies that balance regulatory compliance with practical limitations and strategic priorities.

To further understand why we expect these behavioral responses, we find [Oliver's \(1991\)](#) institutional factors (1) Cause, (2) Constituents and (3) Control to be of highest applicability for our findings. (1) When a firm anticipates that conformity to external pressure will enhance its social legitimacy, it is also more likely to respond with acquiescence ([Oliver, 1991](#)). Our results showed that the interview participants generally agreed with CSRD's cause of increasing the quality of ESG disclosures, creating a more homogeneous reporting framework, and ultimately contributing to a sustainable development, thereby indicating acquiescence. This is also expressed in their voluntary reporting prior to the CSRD in the pursuit of legitimacy. (2) Further, [Oliver \(1991\)](#) argues that when multiplicity in constituents, i.e. the degree of multiple (conflicting) expectations on one company is high, acquiescence as a behavioral response will be low – and vice versa. Due to its legislative nature, the main constituents of the CSRD are national governments, which implement the directive at the national level. This results in a low multiplicity of constituents, thereby promoting acquiescence. However, we showed that also other constituents exert institutional pressures catalyzed by the CSRD. Varying interpretations of the framework by the reporting companies' different stakeholders such as financial institutions, consultants, assurance providers and value chain partners could thereby influence whether agrifood companies will pursue a more proactive or defensive approach to the framework. (3) This also relates to [Oliver's \(1991\)](#) factors of control, i.e. how the pressures are exerted, arguing that legal coercion causes higher acquiescence. While we highlighted the legal coercive pressure of the CSRD, we showed that normative and mimetic mechanisms inside the agrifood value chain can play an equally important role. This agrees with [Lee \(2011\)](#), who argues that firms' CSR related responses to different institutional pressures depend not only on these pressures themselves, but how strong or weak they are enacted by the firms' powerful stakeholders. Our results highlight that this is of specific relevance for the farmers in the agrifood companies' value chains. While these farmers do not experience direct legal coercion, they nevertheless experience indirect institutional pressures from various stakeholders. The high multiplicity in the constituents that pressure farmers could cause them to take a more defensive stance to the reporting of farm-level ESG data. Accordingly, for farmers to show acquiescence, the data requirements that they receive from various stakeholders should be harmonized to reduce multiplicity.

6.1 Embedding in Danish agricultural landscape

Our analysis did not focus on an individual organization or specific group of organizations, but used a wider, sectoral lens with a specific focus on the relationship between companies and farmers. Therefore, we argue that the described interplay of pressures catalyzed by the CSRD should not be seen in isolation, but in connection with other institutional pressures of the agrifood sector both from private and public schemes to better understand and contextualize its implications.

We observe that the pressure for farmers to report on sustainability related information is influenced by several mechanisms. For farm-level disclosure of climate and ESG information, the Danish agricultural advisory service SEGES has released two tools which are already distributed in the Danish sector: One for the calculation of farm-level GHG emissions (ESGreen Tool Climate) and one for farm-level disclosure of other ESG-related topics (ESGreen Tool Report) ([SEGES Innovation, 2024](#)). Further, the Danish dairy cooperative Arla introduced a sustainability incentive model for their dairy farms, paying price premiums to farmers for implementing more environmentally friendly production methods on their farms ([Arla Foods, 2022](#)) and Danish Crown introduced "Climate Track", which enables their value chain farmers to collect farm-level data on GHG emissions, biodiversity, animal welfare and social responsibility ([Danish Crown, 2023](#)).

Beyond food producers, also Danish financial institutions partake in the request for more farm-level sustainability information, already prior to the CSRD. As an example, the Danish bank Nykredit is offering their farm lenders free access to SEGES's ESGreen Tool and helps them to develop climate-action plans and (Madsen, 2023). The data requirements for ESG reporting further go hand-in-hand with other current sustainability trends in the agricultural sector, such as the increasing development of carbon farming schemes (Paul *et al.*, 2023). On the Danish market, this is for example seen in the collaboration between the Danish Carbon Farming Start-Up Agreea and the agrifood cooperative DanishAgro (Agreena, 2022) or in corporate regenerative agriculture strategies, such as by the Danish brewer Carlsberg (2023). These private initiatives have in common that they require farm-level sustainability information to sufficiently function. Also, on the public end further pressures for agricultural sustainability information is increasingly seen in Denmark. In 2024, an agreement was reached to introduce a carbon tax on livestock farming as the first country in the world, accompanied by several other sustainability targets for the agricultural sector (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark, 2024). Further, the Danish Agricultural Agency announced the development of a new regulatory model which aims to support farmers' effort to reduce GHG and nitrate emissions from their farms, fostering the need for farm-level data (Danish Agricultural Agency, 2023).

As we see in the Danish case, the institutional pressures catalyzed by the CSRD are entangled with a landscape of other public and private pressures for a higher sustainability data demand in the agrifood sector. This landscape likely differs between the EU states, due to heterogenic agricultural conditions and value chains (Fanelli, 2019) and certain elements of it, like the close connection between farmers and companies due to their organizational structure of cooperatives, are uniquely found in Denmark. When analyzing the implications of the CSRD for other regions or also other sectors, we thus suggest expanding the analysis beyond looking at the coercive relationship between the directive and targeted companies in isolation and to instead consider wider effects in the value chain and the sectoral interconnectivity with other potential pressures that drive similar organizational responses.

6.2 Sustainability impact or bureaucratic burden?

We lastly want to discuss whether our findings provide insights into the extent to which CSRD reporting can drive a sustainable transition in the agrifood sector. The results revealed uncertainty among informants about whether the increased reporting under the CSRD will induce a positive sustainability impact on a farm level.

As highlighted previously, most ESG literature in the agrifood sector focuses on the relationship between ESG reporting and its financial effects on corporate level. Few studies investigate the correlation between ESG reporting and sustainability performance (Aluchna *et al.*, 2022), and we are not aware of any study doing so specifically for the agrifood sector. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that the disclosure of ESG indicators is an integral part of solving sustainability challenges, e.g. through driving innovation (Zhou *et al.*, 2023), and that compliance with ESG principles can be one of several drivers for sustainable businesses' practices (Xu *et al.*, 2020). Further, engagement with ESG reporting frameworks can reduce ESG decoupling (Li and Wu, 2020), which describes the gap the ESG disclosure of company and its actual ESG performance (García-Sánchez *et al.*, 2022). This effect was also observed after the implementation of the NFRD (Aboud *et al.*, 2023).

On the contrary, Wassénus *et al.* (2024) argue that current sustainability reporting frameworks (including the CSRD) have major shortcomings which hinder their sustainability impact. Despite the introduced double materiality assessment of the CSRD, there is still a strong bias toward financial materiality in the materiality assessment, which risks overseeing material negative corporate environmental issues. Further, the responsibility of assessing material environmental impacts is put on the reporting companies themselves, which potentially use untransparent and differing ways to assess materiality. Besides, often relative

data is used to report on incremental progress, rather than absolute data. This inherently produces subjectivity in the reports, hinders the possibilities to compare different reports and impedes the calculation of aggregated and cumulative environmental effects (Wassénus *et al.*, 2024).

The effectiveness of ESG reporting in driving a positive sustainability impact is thus closely tied to the quality and harmonization of the underlying data. For the agrifood sector, this highlights the need for high quality farm-level data, as most of the negative impacts of food companies happen in the value chain (Harwatt *et al.*, 2024; Poore and Nemecek, 2018). Farm-level sustainability information is often collected through digital assessment tools such as RISE (Hani *et al.*, 2003), which while not specifically designed for ESG reporting, can provide insights into how data collection and management can influence sustainability impacts under the CSRD. Similar to ESG reporting, the link between digital agricultural platforms and their potential to drive farm-level sustainability is not sufficiently analyzed (Chkarat *et al.*, 2023) and the contribution of agricultural sustainability assessment tools to a sustainable development at farm level has previously been challenged (Alrøe and Noe, 2016), among other reasons because a lack of credibility, legitimacy and lack of salience to farm management considerations (de Olde, 2017). Similar to the call of Wassénus *et al.* (2024) to reduce subjectivity in ESG reporting, it has been highlighted that using multiple farm sustainability assessment tools can lead to contradicting results and conclusions about farm sustainability performance (de Olde *et al.*, 2017). This further emphasizes that standardization of farm-level data is necessary to enable the reporting to contribute to a sustainability impact.

Data harmonization is not only desirable to increase the potential of ESG reporting in improving sustainability performance of the agrifood sector, but it would also deliver the positive side effect of reducing the anticipated bureaucratic burden of ESG reporting under the CSRD, which was criticized by several informants in our interviews, especially the potential risk that farmers need to report different data under multiple schemes for different companies. This concurs with Poppe *et al.* (2023) who anticipate an increased demand for farm-level sustainability data, driven by more stringent sustainability policies like the CSRD, and therefore stress the need for harmonized, less cumbersome digital farm sustainability reporting platforms. Due to a higher data demand, several informants mentioned that an increased pressure for data reporting could be a driver for the structural development of Danish farms, potentially causing them to give up production. As highlighted in Section 6.1, one should be careful to see the CSRD in isolation as a sole driver for this, but rather in connection with other pressures for sustainability related information in the sector. Nevertheless, when sustainability is regarded from a three-pillar perspective (social, economic, environmental) (Purvis *et al.*, 2019), a potential trade-off between economic viability and the uncertain sustainability impact of farm-level ESG disclosure should be considered.

Our results suggest that data harmonization will largely depend on the choices of individual food companies regarding data collection from their value-chain farmers. Even with high quality, harmonized data available, farm management decisions will still rely on various factors, including farmers' motivation to implement more sustainable practices (de Olde, 2017), which are often not only profit oriented and dependent on moral considerations (Kemp *et al.*, 2014).

We therefore anticipate the sustainability impact of the CSRD on the Danish food sector to be company- and farm specific. As highlighted, the behavioral responses to the directive are expected to be nuanced, encompassing a spectrum of strategies that balance regulatory compliance with practical constraints and strategic priorities. If the framework can initiate the collection of high-quality, harmonized farm-level data, it holds the potential to contribute to the sector's sustainable transition – provided that it is leveraged to inform strategic organizational decision making. In Denmark, efforts are already made to achieve a better harmonization of farm-level ESG data reporting under the CSRD by the agricultural innovation and consulting company SEGES (personal communication). With Denmark already being a country with a digitalization of the agricultural sector, we argue that the need

for a better farm-level data availability and harmonization will be even more so relevant in other European countries under the CSRD.

7. Conclusions

This study reveals manifold anticipated implications of the CSRD for Danish food companies and farmers, exerted not only through coercive pressure in its legislative form but also through normative pressures and mimetic behavior. The findings suggest acquiescence as the most likely response to these pressures, although associated with high human, organizational and financial resources. Albeit foremost targeted at companies, the ripple effect of the CSRD is seen throughout the value chain, especially by farmers in the form of a higher data demand. We highlight that these pressures are part of a broader landscape of sustainability initiatives inside the Danish agrifood sector, and that they therefore should not be seen in isolation but concurrently with other pressures that drive a sectoral demand for sustainability information.

We added to institutional theory's understanding of how mandatory ESG reporting frameworks enact institutional pressures and how the nature of these different pressures influences the behavioral responses of different actors in the agrifood value chain in relation to ESG reporting. We explicitly highlight the need to look beyond single organizations and instead apply a sectoral lens to get a better understanding of how ESG reporting frameworks enact their pressures.

Our study has several limitations which also present opportunities for future research to build upon our findings. Institutional theory highlights that the institutional setting in which an organization operates strongly influences its behavior. Thus, due to our geographical limitation to the Danish agrifood sector, we suggest further research in different EU countries and/or sectors to widen the understanding of the sectoral institutional pressures exerted by the CSRD. Further, due to the exploratory nature of this study, we cannot draw definite conclusions yet about how firms will behave under the CSRD and how and what they will actually report on. Future research will be necessary to examine organizational behavior under the directive once it has been fully implemented and operational for a period.

Lastly, for ESG reporting to be a meaningful contributor to a sectoral sustainability transition, we stress the need for high quality, farm-level data and highlight the need for future research on how the increased (farm-level) data collection and reporting can be utilized to strategically enhance this transition, rather than to merely accompany it. This carries implications for both academia and practice. We welcome a wider discourse of how reporting under the CSRD can be optimized to contribute to a sustainable development, with participation of more scholars from outside the field of management and accounting studies and research that moves beyond the hitherto strong financial focus. For practitioners in the agrifood sector, it requires both managerial positions in agrifood companies and policymakers to work together toward a harmonization of farm-level sustainability data to move beyond mere compliance with the CSRD and instead use it strategically to accelerate the sustainable transition of the sector, as well as to reduce the often-criticized bureaucratic burden of the framework, especially for farmers.

List of References

- Abate, G., Basile, I. and Ferrari, P. (2021), "The level of sustainability and mutual fund performance in Europe: an empirical analysis using ESG ratings", *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, Vol. 28 No. 5, pp. 1446-1455, doi: [10.1002/csr.2175](https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2175).
- Aboud, A., Saleh, A. and Eliwa, Y. (2023), "Does mandating ESG reporting reduce ESG decoupling? Evidence from the European Union's Directive 2014/95", *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 1305-1320, doi: [10.1002/bse.3543](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3543).
- Adams, W. (2015), "Conducting semi-structured interviews", in *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*, John Wiley & Sons, pp. 492-505, doi: [10.1002/9781119171386.ch19](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19).

- Agreena (2022), “Danish Agro and Agreena enter partnership on carbon certificates”, available at: <https://agreena.com/blog/press-release-danish-agro-and-agreena-enter-partnership-on-carbon-certificates/> (accessed 19 January 2024).
- Alrøe, H.F. and Noe, E. (2016), “Sustainability assessment and complementarity”, *Ecology and Society*, Vol. 21 No. 1, art30, doi: [10.5751/es-08220-210130](https://www.jstor.org/stable/26270352), available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26270352>
- Aluchna, M., Roszkowska-Menkes, M. and Kamiński, B. (2022), “From talk to action: the effects of the non-financial reporting directive on ESG performance”, *Meditari Accountancy Research*, Vol. 31 No. 7, pp. 1-25, doi: [10.1108/MEDAR-12-2021-1530](https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-12-2021-1530).
- Anguiano-Santos, C. and Salazar-Ordóñez, M. (2024), “Sustainability reporting as a tool for fostering sustainable growth in the agri-food sector: the case of Spain”, *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, Vol. 67 No. 2, pp. 426-453, doi: [10.1080/09640568.2022.2115346](https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2022.2115346).
- Arla Foods (2022), “Arla to reward farmers for sustainability actions with new incentive model”, available at: <https://www.arlafoods.co.uk/food-for-thought/sustainability-incentive-and-climate-check/> (accessed 19 January 2024).
- Arvidsson, S. and Dumay, J. (2022), “Corporate ESG reporting quantity, quality and performance: where to now for environmental policy and practice?”, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 31 No. 3, pp. 1091-1110, doi: [10.1002/bse.2937](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2937).
- Aureli, S., Del Baldo, M., Lombardi, R. and Nappo, F. (2020), “Nonfinancial reporting regulation and challenges in sustainability disclosure and corporate governance practices”, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 29 No. 6, pp. 2392-2403, doi: [10.1002/bse.2509](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2509).
- Averbuch, B., Hvarregaard Thorsøe, M. and Kjeldsen, C. (2021), “Longue durée study of agricultural transitions in Denmark using Multi-Level Perspective”, *Geografisk Tidsskrift-Danish Journal of Geography*, Vol. 121 No. 1, pp. 30-45, doi: [10.1080/00167223.2021.1886958](https://doi.org/10.1080/00167223.2021.1886958).
- Baks, M. (2024), “The potential impact of the CSRD and other sustainability legislation on listed companies”, *European Company Law*, Vol. 21 No. 1, pp. 23-29, doi: [10.54648/eucl2024003](https://doi.org/10.54648/eucl2024003).
- Beck, T. (2024), “Accounting for sustainability: the new corporate sustainability reporting directive”, in Lombardi, R. (Ed.), *Mixing Accounting Regulation and Corporate Accountability in the Era of Non-financial Information, Intangibles and Digitalization. Tornado or SUNshine?*, Sapienza Università Editrice, pp. 43-45, doi: [10.13133/9788893773065](https://doi.org/10.13133/9788893773065).
- Bellantuono, N., Pontrandolfo, P. and Scozzi, B. (2018), “Guiding materiality analysis for sustainability reporting: the case of agri-food sector”, *International Journal of Technology, Policy and Management*, Vol. 18 No. 4, p. 336, doi: [10.1504/ijtpm.2018.096181](https://doi.org/10.1504/ijtpm.2018.096181).
- Boiral, O., Brotherton, M.C., Talbot, D. and Guillaumie, L. (2024), “Assessing and managing environmental, social, and governance risks in agri-food companies”, *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, Vol. 31 No. 6, pp. 5690-5708, doi: [10.1002/csr.2884](https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2884).
- Brunella, A., Federico, D., Roberto, F., Pietro, P. and Madau, F.A. (2024), “Role of environmental, social and governance disclosure in business profitability and cost of debt: an analysis of small Southern Italian agri-food businesses”, *Agribusiness*. doi: [10.1002/agr.21933](https://doi.org/10.1002/agr.21933).
- Buallay, A. (2022a), “Sustainability reporting and agriculture industries’ performance: worldwide evidence”, *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*, Vol. 12 No. 5, pp. 769-790, doi: [10.1108/JADEE-10-2020-0247](https://doi.org/10.1108/JADEE-10-2020-0247).
- Buallay, A. (2022b), “Sustainability reporting in food industry: an innovative tool for enhancing financial performance”, *British Food Journal*, Vol. 124 No. 6, pp. 1939-1958, doi: [10.1108/bfj-01-2021-0053](https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-01-2021-0053).
- Campbell, B.M., Beare, D.J., Bennett, E.M., Hall-Spencer, J.M., Ingram, J.S.I., Jaramillo, F., Ortiz, R., Ramankutty, N., Sayer, J.A. and Shindell, D. (2017), “Agriculture production as a major driver of the Earth system exceeding planetary boundaries”, *Ecology and Society*, Vol. 22 No. 4, art8, doi: [10.5751/es-09595-220408](https://doi.org/10.5751/es-09595-220408), available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26798991>
- Carlsberg (2023), “Zero carbon footprint”, available at: <https://www.carlsberggroup.com/sustainability/our-esg-programme/zero-carbon-footprint/#> (accessed 19 January 2024).

- Chen, B., Han, M.Y., Peng, K., Zhou, S.L., Shao, L., Wu, X.F., Wei, W.D., Liu, S.Y., Li, Z., Li, J.S. and Chen, G.Q. (2018), "Global land-water nexus: agricultural land and freshwater use embodied in worldwide supply chains", *Science of the Total Environment*, Vols 613-614, pp. 931-943, doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.138](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.138).
- Chicchini, D., Carello, L.A. and Cotona, M.L. (2024), "Comparing digital sustainability reporting through the EU and US perspectives", in Lombardi, R. (Ed.), *Mixing Accounting Regulation and Corporate Accountability in the Era of Non-financial Information, Intangibles and Digitalization. Tornado or SUNshine?*, Sapienza Università Editrice, pp. 57-68, doi: [10.13133/9788893773065](https://doi.org/10.13133/9788893773065).
- Chkarat, H., Abidi, T. and Sauvée, L. (2023), "Conditions for a convergence between digital platforms and sustainability in agriculture", *Sustainability*, Vol. 15 No. 19, 14195, doi: [10.3390/su151914195](https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914195).
- Conca, L., Manta, F., Morrone, D. and Toma, P. (2021), "The impact of direct environmental, social, and governance reporting: empirical evidence in European-listed companies in the agri-food sector", *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 1080-1093, doi: [10.1002/bse.2672](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2672).
- Conte, P. (2024), "Corporate disclosure before and after the non-financial reporting directive (NFRD)", in Lombardi, R. (Ed.), *Mixing Accounting Regulation and Corporate Accountability in the Era of Non-financial Information, Intangibles and Digitalization. Tornado or SUNshine?*, Sapienza Università Editrice, pp. 75-84, doi: [10.13133/9788893773065](https://doi.org/10.13133/9788893773065).
- Coppola, A., Ianuario, S., Romano, S. and Viccaro, M. (2020), "Corporate social responsibility in agri-food firms: the relationship between CSR actions and firm's performance", *AIMS Environmental Science*, Vol. 7 No. 6, pp. 542-558, doi: [10.3934/envirosci.2020034](https://doi.org/10.3934/envirosci.2020034).
- Cupertino, S., Vitale, G. and Riccaboni, A. (2021), "Sustainability and short-term profitability in the agri-food sector, a cross-sectional time-series investigation on global corporations", *British Food Journal*, Vol. 123 No. 13, pp. 317-336, doi: [10.1108/bfj-02-2021-0154](https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-02-2021-0154).
- Danish Agricultural Agency (2023), "Ny reguleringsmodel for landbruget", Retrieved 19.01.2024 from, available at: <https://lbst.dk/tvaergaaende/ny-reguleringsmodel-for-landbruget>
- Danish Crown (2023), "Our sustainability programme", Retrieved 20.01.2024 from, available at: <https://www.danishcrown.com/global/sustainability/from-farm-to-fork/farmers/farmers-follow-the-climate-track/>
- de Olde, E.M. (2017), "Sustainable development of agriculture: contribution of farm-level assessment tools", Wageningen University, Wageningen, available at: <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/77a51a36-1623-4a16-829d-d134f1b82723>
- de Olde, E.M., Bokkers, E.A.M. and de Boer, I.J.M. (2017), "The choice of the sustainability assessment tool matters: differences in thematic scope and assessment results", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 136, pp. 77-85, doi: [10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.02.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.02.015).
- Debonne, N., Bürgi, M., Diogo, V., Helfenstein, J., Herzog, F., Levers, C., Mohr, F., Swart, R. and Verburg, P. (2022), "The geography of megatrends affecting European agriculture", *Global Environmental Change*, Vol. 75, 102551, doi: [10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102551](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102551).
- DiMaggio, P.J. and Powell, W.W. (1983), "The iron cage revisited: institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields", *American Sociological Review*, Vol. 48 No. 2, pp. 147-160, doi: [10.2307/2095101](https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101).
- Dinh, T., Husmann, A. and Melloni, G. (2023), "Corporate sustainability reporting in Europe: a scoping review", *Accounting in Europe*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 1-29, doi: [10.1080/17449480.2022.2149345](https://doi.org/10.1080/17449480.2022.2149345).
- European Commission (2023), "ANNEX 1 to the CSRD", available at: https://ec.europa.eu/finance/docs/level-2-measures/csr-d-delegated-act-2023-5303-annex-1_en.pdf
- Fanelli, R.M. (2019), "The (un)sustainability of the land use practices and agricultural production in EU countries", *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, Vol. 76 No. 2, pp. 273-294, doi: [10.1080/00207233.2018.1560761](https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2018.1560761).
- Foley, J.A., Ramankutty, N., Brauman, K.A., Cassidy, E.S., Gerber, J.S., Johnston, M., Mueller, N.D., O'Connell, C., Ray, D.K., West, P.C., Balzer, C., Bennett, E.M., Carpenter, S.R., Hill, J., Monfreda, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Sheehan, J., Siebert, S., Tilman, D. and Zaks, D.P.M. (2011), "Solutions for a cultivated planet", *Nature*, Vol. 478 No. 7369, pp. 337-342, doi: [10.1038/nature10452](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10452).

- García-Sánchez, I.M., Hussain, N., Aibar-Guzmán, C. and Aibar-Guzmán, B. (2022), "Assurance of corporate social responsibility reports: does it reduce decoupling practices?", *Business Ethics, the Environment and Responsibility*, Vol. 31 No. 1, pp. 118-138, doi: [10.1111/beer.12394](https://doi.org/10.1111/beer.12394).
- Hani, F., Braga, F., Stampfli, A., Keller, T., Fischer, M. and Porsche, H. (2003), "RISE, a tool for holistic sustainability assessment at the farm level", *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 78-90.
- Harwatt, H., Benton, T.G., Bengtsson, J., Birgisdóttir, B.E., Brown, K.A., Van Dooren, C., Erkkola, M., Graversgaard, M., Halldorsson, T., Hauschild, M., Høyer-Lund, A., Meinilä, J., Van Oort, B., Saarinen, M., Tuomisto, H.L., Trolle, E., Ögmundarson, O. and Blomhoff, R. (2024), "Environmental sustainability of food production and consumption in the Nordic and Baltic region - a scoping review for Nordic Nutrition Recommendations 2023", *Food and Nutrition Research*, Vol. 68, 10539, doi: [10.29219/fnr.v68.10539](https://doi.org/10.29219/fnr.v68.10539).
- Herold, D. (2018), "Demystifying the link between institutional theory and stakeholder theory in sustainability reporting", *Economics, Management and Sustainability*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 6-19, doi: [10.14254/jems.2018.3-2.1](https://doi.org/10.14254/jems.2018.3-2.1).
- Higgins, C. and Larringa, C. (2014), "Sustainability reporting: insights from institutional theory", in Bebbington, J., Unerman, J. and O'Dwyer, B. (Eds), *Sustainability Accounting and Accountability*, 2 ed., Taylor & Francis Group, p. 300, doi: [10.4324/9781315848419](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315848419).
- Hirsch, P.M. (1975), "Organizational effectiveness and the institutional environment", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 20 No. 3, pp. 327-344, doi: [10.2307/2391994](https://doi.org/10.2307/2391994).
- Hoffman, A.J. (1999), "Institutional evolution and change: environmentalism and the U.S. Chemical industry", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 42 No. 4, pp. 351-371, doi: [10.2307/257008](https://doi.org/10.2307/257008).
- Jain, K. and Tripathi, P.S. (2023), "Mapping the environmental, social and governance literature: a bibliometric and content analysis", *Journal of Strategy and Management*, Vol. 16 No. 3, pp. 397-428, doi: [10.1108/jisma-05-2022-0092](https://doi.org/10.1108/jisma-05-2022-0092).
- Kemp, R.G.M., Nijhoff-Savvaki, R., Ruitenburg, R., Trienekens, J.H. and Omta, S.W.F. (2014), "Sustainability-related innovation adoption: the case of the Dutch pig farmer", *Journal on Chain and Network Sciences*, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 69-78, doi: [10.3920/jcns2014.0240](https://doi.org/10.3920/jcns2014.0240).
- Klimek, B. and Hansen, H.O. (2017), "Food industry structure in Norway and Denmark since the 1990s", *Food Policy*, Vol. 69, pp. 110-122, doi: [10.1016/j.foodpol.2017.03.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2017.03.009).
- Krasodomska, J., Simnett, R. and Street, D.L. (2021), "Extended external reporting assurance: current practices and challenges", *Journal of International Financial Management and Accounting*, Vol. 32 No. 1, pp. 104-142, doi: [10.1111/jifm.12127](https://doi.org/10.1111/jifm.12127).
- Krasodomska, J., Zarzycka, E. and Zieniuk, P. (2024), "Voluntary sustainability reporting assurance in the European Union before the advent of the corporate sustainability reporting directive: the country and firm-level impact of Sustainable Development Goals", *Sustainable Development*, Vol. 32 No. 3, pp. 1652-1664, doi: [10.1002/sd.2744](https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2744).
- Kunz, N., Chesney, T., Trautrimis, A. and Gold, S. (2023), "Adoption and transferability of joint interventions to fight modern slavery in food supply chains", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 258, 108809, doi: [10.1016/j.ijpe.2023.108809](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2023.108809).
- Latif, B., Mahmood, Z., Tze San, O., Mohd Said, R. and Bakhsh, A. (2020), "Coercive, normative and mimetic pressures as drivers of environmental management accounting adoption", *Sustainability*, Vol. 12 No. 11, p. 4506, doi: [10.3390/su12114506](https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114506).
- Lee, M.-D.P. (2011), "Configuration of external influences: the combined effects of institutions and stakeholders on corporate social responsibility strategies", *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 102 No. 2, pp. 281-298, doi: [10.1007/s10551-011-0814-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-011-0814-0).
- Leite De Almeida, A.C., Dale, A., Hay, R., Everingham, Y. and Lockie, S. (2024), "Environmental, social and governance (ESG) in agriculture: trends and gaps on research", *Australasian Journal of Environmental Management*, pp. 1-30, doi: [10.1080/14486563.2024.2430313](https://doi.org/10.1080/14486563.2024.2430313).
- Li, J. and Wu, D.A. (2020), "Do corporate social responsibility engagements lead to real environmental, social, and governance impact?", *Management Science*, Vol. 66 No. 6, pp. 2564-2588, doi: [10.1287/mnsc.2019.3324](https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2019.3324).

- Livesey, S.M. (2001), "Eco-identity as discursive struggle: royal Dutch/shell, brent spar, and Nigeria", *Journal of Business Communication*, Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. 58-91, doi: [10.1177/002194360103800105](https://doi.org/10.1177/002194360103800105).
- Madsen, T.N. (2023), "Nykredit giver landbrugskunder gratis adgang til klimaværktøj", available at: https://finanswatch.dk/Finansnyt/Pengeinstitutter/nykredit_bank/article16694314.ece (accessed 22 January 2024).
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark (2024), "Insight: Denmark is the first country in the world to introduce carbon tax on livestock farming", available at: <https://investindk.com/insights/denmark-is-the-first-country-in-the-world-to-introduce-carbon-tax-on-livestock-farming> (accessed 8 January 2024).
- Nirino, N., Miglietta, N. and Salvi, A. (2019), "The impact of corporate social responsibility on firms' financial performance, evidence from the food and beverage industry", *British Food Journal*, Vol. 122 No. 1, pp. 1-13, doi: [10.1108/bfj-07-2019-0503](https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-07-2019-0503).
- Oliver, C. (1991), "Strategic responses to institutional processes", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 145-179, doi: [10.2307/258610](https://doi.org/10.2307/258610).
- Orou Sannou, R., Kirschke, S. and Günther, E. (2023), "Integrating the social perspective into the sustainability assessment of agri-food systems: a review of indicators", *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, Vol. 39, pp. 175-190, doi: [10.1016/j.spc.2023.05.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.05.014).
- Ottenstein, P., Erben, S., Jost, S., Weuster, C.W. and Zülch, H. (2022), "From voluntarism to regulation: effects of Directive 2014/95/EU on sustainability reporting in the EU", *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, Vol. 23 No. 1, pp. 55-98, doi: [10.1108/jaar-03-2021-0075](https://doi.org/10.1108/jaar-03-2021-0075).
- Paul, C., Bartkowski, B., Donmez, C., Don, A., Mayer, S., Steffens, M., Weigl, S., Wiesmeier, M., Wolf, A. and Helming, K. (2023), "Carbon farming: are soil carbon certificates a suitable tool for climate change mitigation?", *Journal of Environmental Management*, Vol. 330, 117142, doi: [10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.117142](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.117142).
- Pinheiro, A.B., Dos Santos, J.I.A.S., Cherobim, A.P.M.S. and Segatto, A.P. (2023), "What drives environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance? The role of institutional quality", *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 427-444, doi: [10.1108/meq-03-2023-0091](https://doi.org/10.1108/meq-03-2023-0091).
- Pirtea, M.G., Noja, G.G., Cristea, M. and Panait, M. (2021), "Interplay between environmental, social and governance coordinates and the financial performance of agricultural companies", *Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 67 No. 12, pp. 479-490, doi: [10.17221/286/2021-AGRICECON](https://doi.org/10.17221/286/2021-AGRICECON).
- Poore, J. and Nemecek, T. (2018), "Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers", *Science*, Vol. 360 No. 6392, pp. 987-992, doi: [10.1126/science.aag0216](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0216).
- Poppe, K., Vrolijk, H. and Bosloper, I. (2023), "Integration of farm financial accounting and farm management information systems for better sustainability reporting", *Electronics*, Vol. 12 No. 6, p. 1485, doi: [10.3390/electronics12061485](https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12061485).
- Purvis, B., Mao, Y. and Robinson, D. (2019), "Three pillars of sustainability: in search of conceptual origins", *Sustainability Science*, Vol. 14 No. 3, pp. 681-695, doi: [10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5).
- Sandberg, H., Alnoor, A. and Tiberius, V. (2022), "Environmental, social, and governance ratings and financial performance: evidence from the European food industry", *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 32 No. 4, pp. 2471-2489, doi: [10.1002/bse.3259](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3259).
- SEGES Innovation (2024), *ESGreenTool® – the digital solution for environmental, social, and governance (ESG) reporting in agriculture*, available at: https://segesinnovation.com/products-and-services/digital-solutions/esgreentool/?_gl=1*1cbxz4o*_gcl_au*MTQwNjYzMTUzMi4xNzI4OTk5MTE2*_ga*MTA4Mzk4ODkxNS4xNzI4OTk5MTE2*_ga_2B7JJ40N8H*MTcyODk5OTExNi4xLjAuMTcyODk5OTExNi4wLjAuMA (accessed 15 January 2024).
- Senadheera, S.S., Gregory, R., Rinklebe, J., Farrukh, M., Rhee, J.H. and Ok, Y.S. (2022), "The development of research on environmental, social, and governance (ESG): a bibliometric analysis", *Sustainable Environment*, Vol. 8 No. 1, doi: [10.1080/27658511.2022.2125869](https://doi.org/10.1080/27658511.2022.2125869).
- Șerbănel, C.-I. (2021), "A panorama of digitalization tendencies in the European agriculture sector", *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, Vol. 15 pp. 352-363, doi: [10.2478/picbe-2021-0033](https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2021-0033).

- Tao, S., Xu, Y., Liu, K., Pan, J. and Gou, S. (2011), "Research progress in agricultural vulnerability to climate change", *Advances in Climate Change Research*, Vol. 2 No. 4, pp. 203-210, doi: [10.3724/SPJ.1248.2011.00203](https://doi.org/10.3724/SPJ.1248.2011.00203).
- Vitale, G., Cupertino, S. and Riccaboni, A. (2023), "The effects of mandatory non-financial reporting on financial performance. A multidimensional investigation on global agri-food companies", *British Food Journal*, Vol. 125 No. 13, pp. 99-124, doi: [10.1108/bfj-06-2022-0545](https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-06-2022-0545).
- Wassénius, E., Crona, B. and Quahe, S. (2024), "Essential environmental impact variables: a means for transparent corporate sustainability reporting aligned with planetary boundaries", *One Earth*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 211-225, doi: [10.1016/j.oneear.2024.01.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.01.014).
- Weber, O. (2014), "Environmental, social and governance reporting in China", *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 23 No. 5, pp. 303-317, doi: [10.1002/bse.1785](https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1785).
- Willett, W., Rockström, J., Loken, B., Springmann, M., Lang, T., Vermeulen, S., Garnett, T., Tilman, D., Declerck, F., Wood, A., Jonell, M., Clark, M., Gordon, L.J., Fanzo, J., Hawkes, C., Zurayk, R., Rivera, J.A., De Vries, W., Majele Sibanda, L., Afshin, A., Chaudhary, A., Herrero, M., Agustina, R., Branca, F., Lartey, A., Fan, S., Crona, B., Fox, E., Bignet, V., Troell, M., Lindahl, T., Singh, S., Cornell, S.E., Srinath Reddy, K., Narain, S., Nishtar, S. and Murray, C.J.L. (2019), "Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems", *The Lancet*, Vol. 393, 10170, pp. 447-492, doi: [10.1016/s0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(18)31788-4).
- WSSD (2002), "Report of the world summit on sustainable development, Johannesburg, South Africa, 26 August-4 September 2002", World Summit on Sustainable Development (2002 : Johannesburg, South Africa), available at: <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/478154>
- Xu, J., Liu, F. and Shang, Y. (2020), "R&D investment, ESG performance and green innovation performance: evidence from China", *Kybernetes*, Vol. 50 No. 3, pp. 737-756, doi: [10.1108/K-12-2019-0793](https://doi.org/10.1108/K-12-2019-0793).
- Zhou, S., Rashid, M.H.U., Mohd Zobair, S.A., Sobhani, F.A. and Siddik, A.B. (2023), "Does ESG impact firms' sustainability performance? The mediating effect of innovation performance", *Sustainability*, Vol. 15 No. 6, p. 5586, doi: [10.3390/su15065586](https://doi.org/10.3390/su15065586).

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